

Intuitionistic Fuzzy Environments and Hausdroff Distances¹

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Abstract

The Hausdroff distance is a fundamental metric in mathematics for measuring the separation between subsets in a metric space. Its extension to interval-valued fuzzy sets and Intuitionistic fuzzy sets (IFSs) enables advanced analysis of uncertainty and vagueness in decision-making problems. This paper explores key concepts, including Hausdroff distances for interval-valued fuzzy sets, representations of IFSs, and ranking methods for Intuitionistic fuzzy alternatives.

Keywords

Hausdroff Distance, Intuitionistic Fuzzy Sets, Decision Making, Intuitionistic fuzzy alternatives.

1 Hausdroff Distances

The Hausdroff distances are important from the point of view of practical applications, namely, in image matching, image analysis, visual navigation of robots, motion tracking, computer – assisted surgery .Although the definition of the Hausdroff distances is simple, the calculations needed to solve the real problems are complex. In result the efficiency of the algorithms for computing the Hausdroff distances may be crucial and the use of some approximations may be relevant and useful

First of all, the formulas proposed for calculating the distances should be formally correct. This is the motivation of this section. Namely, we consider the results of using the Hamming distances between the intuitionistic fuzzy sets calculated in two possible ways– taking into account the two representation (the membership and non-membership values) of the intuitionistic fuzzy sets, and next – taking into account the three term representation (the membership, non-membership values, and hesitation margin values) of the intuitionistic fuzzy sets. We will verify if the resulting distances fulfill the properties of the Hausdroff distances.

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The next problem we consider concerns calculating the Hausdroff distance based on the Hamming metric for the interval – valued fuzzy sets. We prove that the formulas that are effective and efficient for the interval – valued fuzzy sets do not work well in the case of the intuitionistic fuzzy sets.

The Hausdroff distance is 'the maximum distance of a set to the nearest point in the other set'. More formal description is given by the following

Definition . Given two finite sets $A = \{a_1, \dots, a_p\}$ and $B = \{b_1, \dots, b_q\}$, the Hausdroff distance $H(A,B)$ is defined as :

$$H(A, B) = \max\{h(A, B)h(B, A)\}$$

Where

$$h(A, B) = \max_{a \in A} \min_{b \in B} d(a, b)$$

where :

- a and b are elements belonging to sets A and B respectively,
- d (a,b) is any metric between elements a and b,
- the two distances $h(A,B)$ and $h(B,A)$ are called the Hausdroff distances.

The directed Hausdroff distance from A to B, i.e., the function $h(A,B)$ ranks each elements of A based on its distance to the nearest element of B, and then the highest ranked element specifies the value of the distance. Usually, $h(A,B)$ and $h(A,B)$ can be different value (the directed distances are not symmetric).

Following the way of calculating the Hausdroff distances .we may notice that if A and B contain one element each (a_1 and b_1 , respectively), the Hausdroff distance is just equal to $d(a_1, b_1)$. In other words, if for separate elements a formula which is expected to express the Hausdroff distance gives a result which is not consistent with the used metric d(e.g., the Hamming distance, the Euclidean distance, etc.), the formula considered is not a proper definition of the Hausdroff distance).

1.1 The Hausdroff Distance between the Inter-valued Fuzzy Sets

The Hausdroff distance between two intervals : $U = [u_1, u_2]$ and $W = [w_1, w_2]$ is :

$$h(U, W) = \max\{|u_1 - w_1|, |u_2 - w_2|\}$$

Assuming the two-term representation for the intuitionistic fuzzy sets : $A = \{x, \mu_A(x), v_A(x)\}$ and $B = \{x, \mu_B(x), v_B(x)\}$, we may consider the two intuitionistic fuzzy sets, A and B, as two intervals, namely :

$$[\mu_A(x), 1 - v_A(x)] \text{ and } [v_A(x), 1 - v_B(x)]$$

Then

$$h(A, B) = \max\{|\mu_A(x) - \mu_B(x)|, |v_A(x) - v_B(x)|\}$$

Later on we will verify if is a properly calculated Hausdroff distance between the intuitionistic fuzzy sets while using the Hamming metric.

2. Two term Representation of the Intuitionistic Fuzzy Sets and the Hausdroff Distance (Hamming Metric)

Following the algorithm of calculating the directed Hausdroff distances, when applying the two term type Hamming distance between the intuitionistic fuzzy sets, we obtain :

$$d_h(A, B) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \max\{|\mu_A(x_i) - \mu_B(x_i)|, |v_A(x_i) - v_B(x_i)|\}$$

If the above distance is a properly calculated Hausdroff distance, then in the case of degenerate, i.e., one-element sets $A = \{(x, \mu_A(x) - v_A(x))\}$ and $B = \{(x, \mu_B(x) - v_B(x))\}$, it should give the same results as the two term type Hamming distance. It means that in the case of the two term type Hamming distance, for the degenerate, one element intuitionistic fuzzy sets, the following equations should give just the same results:

$$l_{IFS(2)}(A, B) = \frac{1}{2} (|\mu_A(x) - \mu_B(x)| + (|v_A(x) - v_B(x)|))$$

$$d_h(A, B) = \max(|\mu_A(x) - \mu_B(x)| + (|v_A(x) - v_B(x)|))$$

Where is the normalized two term type Hamming distance, and should be its counterpart Hausdroff distance.

We will verify on a simple example that gives the same results as they should do following the essence of the Hausdroff measures.

2.1 Example: (Szmidt and Kacprzyk) Consider the following one-element intuitionistic fuzzy sets :

$$A, B, D, G, E \in X = \{x\}$$

$$A = \{<x, 1, 0>\}, B = \{<x, 0, 1, >\}, d = \{<x, 0, 0>\}, g = \{<x, 1/2, 1/2, >\}, E = \{<x, 1/4, 1/4 >\}$$

The results are :

$$d_h(A, B) = \max\{|1 - 0|, |0 - 1|\} = 1$$

$$d_h(A, D) = \max\{|1 - 0|, |0 - 0|\} = 1$$

$$d_h(B, D) = \max\{|0 - 0|, |1 - 0|\} = 1$$

$$d_h(A, G) = \max\{|1 - 1/2|, |0 - 1/2|\} = 0.5$$

$$d_h(A, E) = \max\{|1 - 1/4|, |0 - 1/4|\} = 0.75$$

$$d_h(B, G) = \max\{|0 - 1/2|, |1 - 1/2|\} = 0.5$$

$$d_h(B, E) = \max\{|0 - 1/4|, |1 - 1/4|\} = 0.75$$

$$d_h(D, G) = \max\{|0 - 1/2|, |0 - 1/2|\} = 0.5$$

$$d_h(D, E) = \max\{|0 - 1/4|, |1 - 1/4|\} = 0.25$$

$$d_h(G, E) = \max\{|1/2 - 1/4|, |1/2 - 1/4|\} = 0.25$$

Their counterpart Hamming distances calculated from are :

$$l_{IFS(2)}(A, B) = 0.5\{|1 - 0| + |0 - 1|\} = 1$$

$$l_{IFS(2)}(A, D) = 0.5\{|1 - 0| + |0 - 0|\} = 0.5$$

$$l_{IFS(2)}(B, D) = 0.5\{|0 - 0| + |1 - 0|\} = 0.5$$

$$l_{IFS(2)}(A, G) = 0.5\{|0 - 1/2| + |0 - 1/2|\} = 0.5$$

$$l_{IFS(2)}(A, E) = 0.5\{|1 - 1/4| + |0 - 1/4|\} = 0.5$$

$$l_{IFS(2)}(B, G) = 0.5\{|1 - 1/4| + |0 - 1/4|\} = 0.5$$

$$l_{IFS(2)}(B, E) = 0.5\{|1 - 1/4| + |0 - 1/4|\} = 0.5$$

$$l_{IFS(2)}(D, G) = 0.5\{|0 - 1/2| + |0 - 1/2|\} = 0.5$$

$$l_{IFS(2)}(D, E) = 0.5\{|0 - 1/4| + |0 - 1/4|\} = 0.25$$

$$l_{IFS(2)}(G, E) = 0.5\{|1/2 - 1/4| + |1/2 - 1/4|\} = 0.25$$

i.e. the values of the Hamming distances used to define the Hausdroff measures, and the values of the resulting Hausdroff distances calculated for the separate elements are not consistent (as they should be). The differences are :

$$d_h(A, D) \neq l_{IFS(2)}(A, D)$$

$$d_h(B, D) \neq l_{IFS(2)}(B, D)$$

$$d_h(A, E) \neq l_{IFS(2)}(A, E)$$

$$d_h(B, E) \neq l_{IFS(2)}(B, E)$$

It is easy to show that the inconsistencies as shown above occur for an infinite number of other cases. Now we will verify the conditions under which the equations give consistent results, i.e., when for the separate elements we have (Szmidt and Kacprzyk):

$$\frac{1}{2}(|\mu_A(x) - \mu_B(x)| + (|v_A(x) - v_B(x)|)) = \max\{|\mu_A(x) - \mu_B(x)|, (|v_A(x) - v_B(x)|)\}$$

Taking into account that

$$\mu_A(x) + v_A(x) + \pi_A(x) = 1$$

$$\mu_B(x) + v_B(x) + \pi_B(x) = 1$$

we obtain

$$(\mu_A(x) - \mu_B(x)) + (v_A(x) - v_B(x)) + (\pi_A(x) - \pi_B(x)) = 0$$

It is easy to notice that above equation is not fulfilled for all elements belonging to an intuitionistic fuzzy set but for some elements only. is fulfilled for the following conditions of (Szmidt and Kacprzyk)

- For $\pi_A(x) - \pi_B(x) = 0$, we have
 $|\mu_A(x) - \mu_B(x)| = |v_A(x) - v_B(x)|$
 and having in mind of above, we can express the above equation in the following way :
 $0.5(|\mu_A(x) - \mu_B(x)| + |\mu_A(x) - \mu_B(x)|) = \max\{|\mu_A(x) - \mu_B(x)|, |\mu_A(x) - \mu_B(x)|\}$
- If $\pi_A(x) - \pi_B(x) \neq 0$ but, at the same time
 $\mu_A(x) - \mu_B(x) = v_A(x) - v_B(x) = \frac{1}{2}(\pi_A(x) - \pi_B(x))$

In the above context it seems to be a bad idea to try constructing the Hausdroff distance using the two term type Hamming distance between the intuitionistic fuzzy sets.

An immediate conclusion is that, relating to the results concerning interval-valued fuzzy sets, the Hausdroff distance for the intuitionistic fuzzy sets can not be constructed in the same way as for the interval-valued fuzzy sets.

3. Three term Hamming Distance Between the Intuitionistic Fuzzy Sets and the Hausdroff Metric

Now we will show that by applying the three term type Hamming distance for the intuitionistic fuzzy sets, we obtain correct (in the sense of Definition) Hausdroff distance.

Namely, if we calculate the three term type Hamming distance between two de-generate, i.e. one-element intuitionistic fuzzy sets, A and B in the spirit of Szmidt and Kacprzyk Szmidt and Baldwin i.e., in the following way :

$$l_{IFS}^1(A, B) = \frac{1}{2} (|\mu_A(x) - \mu_B(x)| + |v_A(x) - v_B(x)| + |\pi_A(x) - \pi_B(x)|)$$

We can give a counterpart of the above distance in terms of the max function (Szmidt and kacprzyk):

$$H_3(A, B) = \max\{|\mu_A(x) - \mu_B(x)|, |v_A(x) - v_B(x)|, |\pi_A(x) - \pi_B(x)|\}$$

If $H_3(A, B)$ is a properly specified Hausdroff distance (in the sense that for two degenerate, one element intuitionistic fuzzy sets, the results is equal to the metric used), the following condition should be fulfilled (Szmidt and Kacprzyk) :

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{2} (|\mu_A(x) - \mu_B(x)| + |v_A(x) - v_B(x)| + |\pi_A(x) - \pi_B(x)|) \\ &= \max\{|\mu_A(x) - \mu_B(x)|, |v_A(x) - v_B(x)|, |\pi_A(x) - \pi_B(x)|\} \end{aligned}$$

Let us verify above equation is valid. Without loss of generality we can assume

$$\max\{|\mu_A(x) - \mu_B(x)|, |v_A(x) - v_B(x)|, |\pi_A(x) - \pi_B(x)|\} = |\mu_A(x) - \mu_B(x)|$$

For $|\mu_A(x) - \mu_B(x)|$ fulfilling the above, we conclude that both $v_A(x) - v_B(x)$, and $\pi_A(x) - \pi_B(x)$ are of the same sign (both values are either positive or negative).

Therefore

$$|\mu_A(x) - \mu_B(x)| = |v_A(x) - v_B(x)| + |\pi_A(x) - \pi_B(x)|$$

we can verify that initial equation is always valid as

$$\begin{aligned} & 0.5\{|\mu_A(x) - \mu_B(x)| + |\mu_A(x) - \mu_B(x)|\} \\ &= \max\{|\mu_A(x) - \mu_B(x)|, |v_A(x) - v_B(x)|, |\pi_A(x) - \pi_B(x)|\} \\ &= |\mu_A(x) - \mu_B(x)| \end{aligned}$$

Now we will use the above formula, for the data used in Example1. But now, as we also take into account the hesitation margins $\pi(x)$ we use the three term, "full" description of the data $\{<x, \mu(x), v(x), \pi(x)\}$, i.e. employing all three functions (the membership, non-membership and hesitation margin) describing the considered intuitionistic fuzzy sets

$$A=\{<x, 1, 0, 0.\}, \quad B=\{<x, 0, 1, 0>\}, \quad D=\{<x, 0, 0, 1>\}, \quad G=\{<x, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, 0>\}, \quad E = \{<x, \frac{1}{4}, \frac{1}{4}, \frac{1}{2}\}$$

we have :

$$\begin{aligned} H_3(A, B) &= \max(|1 - 0|, |0 - 1|, |0 - 0|) = 1 \\ H_3(A, D) &= \max(|1 - 0|, |0 - 0|, |0 - 1|) = 1 \\ H_3(B, D) &= \max(|0 - 0|, |1 - 0|, |0 - 1|) = 1 \\ H_3(A, G) &= \max(|0 - 1/2|, |0 - 1/2|, |0 - 0|) = 0.5 \\ H_3(A, E) &= \max(|1 - 1/4|, |0 - 1/4|, |0 - 1/2|) = 0.75 \\ H_3(B, G) &= \max(|1 - 1/4|, |0 - 1/4|, |0 - 1/2|) = 0.75 \\ H_3(B, E) &= \max(|1 - 1/4|, |0 - 1/4|, |0 - 1/2|) = 0.75 \\ H_3(D, G) &= \max(|0 - 1/2|, |0 - 1/2|, |1 - 0|) = 1 \\ H_3(D, E) &= \max(|0 - 1/4|, |0 - 1/4|, |1 - 1/2|) = 0.5 \\ H_3(G, E) &= \max(|1/2 - 1/4|, |1/2 - 1/4|, |0 - 1/2|) = 0.5 \end{aligned}$$

The counterpart Hamming distances obtained (with all three functions) are

$$l_{IFS}^1(A, B) = 0.5(|1 - 0| + |0 - 1| + |0 - 0|) = 1$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 l_{IFS}^1(A, D) &= 0.5(|1 - 0| + |0 - 0| + |0 - 1|) = 1 \\
 l_{IFS}^1(B, D) &= 0.5(|0 - 0| + |1 - 0| + |0 - 1|) = 1 \\
 l_{IFS}^1(A, G) &= 0.5(|0 - 1/2| + |0 - 1/2| + |0 - 0|) = 0.5 \\
 l_{IFS}^1(A, E) &= 0.5(|1 - 1/4| + |0 - 1/4| + |0 - 1/2|) = 0.75 \\
 l_{IFS}^1(B, G) &= 0.5(|1 - 1/4| + |0 - 1/4| + |0 - 1/2|) = 0.75 \\
 l_{IFS}^1(B, E) &= 0.5(|1 - 1/4| + |0 - 1/4| + |0 - 1/2|) = 0.75 \\
 l_{IFS}^1(D, G) &= 0.5(|0 - 1/2| + |0 - 1/2| + |1 - 0|) = 1 \\
 l_{IFS}^1(D, E) &= 0.5(|0 - 1/4| + |0 - 1/4| + |1 - 1/2|) = 0.5 \\
 l_{IFS}^1(G, E) &= 0.5(|1/2 - 1/4| + |1/2 - 1/4| + |0 - 1/2|) = 0.5
 \end{aligned}$$

As we can see, the Hausdroff distance (using the membership values, non-membership values and hesitation margins) and the three term Hamming distance give for one-element intuitionistic fuzzy sets fully consistent results. The same situation occurs in a general case too.

we can give the following equivalent representation in terms of the max function :

$$H_3(A, B) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \max \{ |\mu_A(x_i) - \mu_B(x_i)|, |v_A(x_i) - v_B(x_i)|, |\pi_A(x_i) - \pi_B(x_i)| \}$$

Unfortunately, it can be easily verified that it is impossible to give the counterpart pairs of the formulas like above in three terms distances for $r > 1$ in the Minkowski r -metrics ($r=1$ is the Hamming distance, $r=2$ is the Euclidean distance, etc.).

Now we will show that the three term distances between the intuitionistic fuzzy sets are useful in the ranking of intuitionistic fuzzy alternatives.

4. Ranking of the Intuitionistic Fuzzy Alternatives

Intuitionistic fuzzy sets are valuable in scenarios involving uncertainty, which has led to their widespread use in fields such as decision making. A key challenge in this context is how to rank intuitionistic fuzzy alternatives—options characterized by their membership, non-membership, and hesitation degrees—especially when these options result from processes like decision analysis or aggregation. In this framework, each alternative is considered an element within a universe of discourse, with associated values indicating the degree to which it meets certain criteria ($\mu(\cdot)$), the degree to which it does not meet those criteria ($v(\cdot)$), and the degree of uncertainty or hesitation regarding its fulfillment ($\pi(\cdot)$). Therefore, alternatives can be represented as intuitionistic fuzzy sets, and for clarity, we refer to these as “intuitionistic fuzzy alternatives.”

Ranking these alternatives is not straightforward, as intuitionistic fuzzy sets lack a natural linear ordering among their elements. This contrasts with traditional fuzzy sets, where elements are easily ordered due to their membership degrees being real numbers within the interval 1.

Ranking alternatives in IFSs relies on score functions such as:

$$S(x) = \mu(x) - v(x)$$

or accuracy functions that incorporate $\pi(x)\pi(x)$. The lack of a natural linear order in IFSs necessitates these auxiliary measures, which are sensitive to both membership dynamics and hesitation. Advanced

ranking methods often integrate Hausdroff distances to refine comparisons, particularly in multi-criteria decision-making.

Conclusion

The three-term representation of IFSs, coupled with the Hamming-based Hausdroff metric, provides a robust framework for quantifying differences between intuitionistic fuzzy alternatives. This approach addresses the limitations of interval-valued and two-term models by explicitly incorporating hesitation margins. Future research should focus on optimizing these metrics for real-world decision-making scenarios, where uncertainty and partial information are pervasive.

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